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CUTANEOUS MELANOMA – CURRENT PROBLEM OF CLINICAL ONCOLOGY

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Abstract

This scientific publication presents modern global and regional data on incidence rate, mortality rate, lethality and five-year survival rates, as well as the prognosis of such a terrible disease as cutaneous melanoma. The geographical features of the prevalence of this disease and current trends are covered in detail. The epidemiological aspects of this pathology in our republic are shown in the context of regions of the country.

Keywords: cutaneous melanoma, epidemiology, incidence rate, mortality rate, lethality, five-year survival rate, prognosis.

As is known, one of the most aggressive forms of skin tumors is cutaneous melanoma, which, for a number of known reasons, is classified as a separate cluster of skin tumors. Cutaneous melanoma is a malignant neoplasm that arises from skin melanocytes. The incidence rate is rising, especially among the white population. Melanoma of the skin usually occurs due to exposure to ultraviolet radiation from natural sunlight and indoor tanning, although there are several subtypes that are not associated with exposure to ultraviolet radiation. Primary melanomas are often darkly pigmented but may be colorless, with diagnosis based on a combination of clinical and histopathological findings. Primary melanoma is treated with wide excision, the margins of which are determined by the thickness of the tumor. Further treatment depends on the stage of the disease (following histopathological examination and, if necessary, sentinel lymph node biopsy) and may include surgery, checkpoint immunotherapy, targeted therapy or radiotherapy. Systemic drug therapy is recommended as an adjunct to surgery in patients with resectable locoregional metastases and is the mainstay of treatment for advanced melanoma. Treatment of advanced melanoma is challenging, especially in patients with brain metastases. Multidisciplinary care is essential. Systemic drug therapies, particularly immune checkpoint inhibitors, have significantly improved sur-

vival in melanoma following a series of landmark approvals beginning in 2011 [1,2].

Melanoma develops as a result of malignant transformations of pigment-producing melanocytes. When located in the basal layer of the epidermis of the skin, melanoma is called cutaneous, which is more common. Australia and New Zealand are world leaders in this regard with an incidence rate of 54/100,000 and a mortality rate of 5.6/100,000 for 2015 [3].

According to the WHO classification of skin tumors published in 2018, melanomas were divided into those that are etiologically related to sun exposure and those that are not, determined by their mutational signature, anatomical location and epidemiology. Melanomas on sun-exposed skin were further divided by the histopathological grade of cumulative sun damage (CSD) of the surrounding skin into low and high CSD based on the degree of associated solar elastosis. Melanomas with low CSD include superficial spreading melanomas, and melanomas with high CSD include lentigo maligna and desmoplastic melanomas. The nonsolar category includes acral melanomas, some congenital nevus melanomas, blue nevus melanomas, Spitz melanomas, mucosal melanomas, and uveal melanomas. The general term “melanocytoma” is thought to cover “intermediate” tumors that have an increased (albeit low) likelihood of disease progression to mela-

noma [4]. Although many cases are preventable, cutaneous melanoma remains the most serious skin cancer worldwide. Understanding the scope and profile of the disease is vital to focusing and strengthening global prevention efforts. Arnold M. et al. [5] examined global patterns of cutaneous melanoma in 2020 and provided projected estimates of incidence rate and mortality rate by 2040. This population-based study used the GLOBOCAN 2020 database to provide a global epidemiological estimate of new cases and deaths from invasive melanoma.

Age-standardized incidence rate and mortality rates were calculated per 100,000 person-years by country, world region, and 4-level human development level. The estimated number of cases and deaths was calculated for 2040. In 2020, it is estimated that there were a total of 325,000 new cases of melanoma (174,000 men, 151,000 women) and 57,000 deaths (32,000 men, 25,000 women) worldwide. The highest incidence rate among men (42 per 100,000 person-years) and women (31 per 100,000 person-years) are observed in Australia/New Zealand, followed by Western Europe (19 per 100,000 person-years for both men and women), North America (18 per 100,000 person-years for men, 14 per 100,000 person-years for women), and Northern Europe (17 per 100,000 person-years for men, 18 per 100,000 person-years for women). Melanoma remained rare in most countries in Africa and Asia, with incidence rate typically less than 1 per 100,000 person-years. Mortality rates peaked at 5 per 100,000 person-years in New Zealand, and geographic variation was less pronounced than incidence rate. In most regions of the world, melanoma was more common among men than women. If 2020 rates continue, the burden of melanoma is estimated to increase to 510,000 new cases (an increase of approximately 50%) and 96,000 deaths (an increase of 68%) by 2040 [5].

This epidemiological assessment shows that melanoma remains an important cancer control and public health problem worldwide, particularly among fair-skinned populations of European ancestry.

The incidence rate of skin melanoma in the Republic of Kazakhstan in 2022 was 1.7 per 100 thousand population, which in absolute numbers amounted to 336 people, occupying 21 ranking places, as in the previous year. The share of cases with a diagnosis established for the first time in their lives, recorded by oncology organizations, was 1.0%. At the same time, 125 men fell ill (specific gravity - 0.8%, rank 16), women - 211 (specific gravity - 1.1%, rank 17) [6]. The incidence rate of skin melanoma was higher than the national average in 8 regions of the country: East Kazakhstan region - 4.4 (maximum indicator); Pavlodar - 3.7; Kostanay - 3.6; Karaganda - 3.5; North Kazakhstan - 2.4; Abay - 2.3; Almaty - 2.0 and Zhetysay - 1.9. The indicator is lower in 11 regions: in Turkestan and Kyzylorda - 0.4 (the lowest indicator); Atyrau region - 0.6; Aktobe - 1.0; Almaty and Shymkent - 1.1; Zhambyl and Astana - 1.2; Mangystau and West Kazakhstan - 1.3 and Akmola - 1.5 regions per 100 thousand population [6].

In the structure of causes of mortality rate for both

sexes, this disease, as well as incidence rate, occupies 21st place, amounting to 0.7%, and in absolute numbers - 92 people (46 men and the same number of women). The regions where the mortality rate from cutaneous melanoma is higher than the national average (0.5 per 100 thousand population) include: Karaganda - 1.2 (maximum level); Abay, East Kazakhstan and Kostanay - 0.8; Pavlodar - 0.7; North Kazakhstan and Almaty - 0.6. In parity with the republican average - Zhambyl region and Astana. The lowest rates were noted in West Kazakhstan - 0.0; Atyrau region - 0.1; Aktobe, Turkestan and Kyzylorda - 0.2; Mangystau, Almaty, Zhetysay, Shymkent - 0.3 and Akmola - 0.4 regions per 100 thousand population [6]. At the same time, the one-year mortality rate was 7.6%. The ratio between one-year mortality and neglect (stage IV) is 1.1. Let us recall that the maximum distance from 1 is the worst ratio between the indicators of one-year mortality rate and neglect. This nosological form of malignant neoplasms, despite its belonging to the most aggressive types of malignant tumors, showed one of the lowest ratios of one-year mortality rate and advanced cancer (stage IV).

It should also be noted that during preventive examinations in 2022, cutaneous melanoma can be classified as one of the most actively detected tumors among all cancer localizations with a significant increase compared to the level of 2021 - 74.3% (62.7% in 2021).

However, despite the fact that cutaneous melanoma belongs to visually accessible localizations, in 2022 the proportion of this form of malignant tumors detected in the early stages (0, I-II stages) of the disease decreased from 91.1 to 88.4%. Apparently, the decrease in the availability of assistance in 2020-2021 during the Covid-19 pandemic is having an impact. At the same time, cutaneous melanoma is classified as a form of malignant tumors with a high proportion of patients with stages I-II in terms of nosologies in the entire republic - 83.9% (82.6% in 2021) [6].

The regions where the proportion of patients with stages I-II of cutaneous melanoma is higher than the national average (83.9%) include the following regions: Atyrau, West Kazakhstan and Kyzylorda - 100%; Pavlodar - 96.4%; Almaty city - 95.5%; Almaty - 94.1%; East Kazakhstan - 93.8%; Astana city - 86.7%; Zhambyl and North Kazakhstan - 84.6%. The lowest rates of early diagnosis were found in Aktobe region - 55.6% (the lowest level); Akmola - 60.0%; Zhetysay - 64.3%; Turkestan - 66.7%; Shymkent city - 69.2%; Abay - 71.4%; Karaganda - 77.1%; Mangystau - 80.0% and Kostanay - 83.3% [6].

The highest level of morphological verification occurs at visually accessible locations of malignant neoplasms. These include cutaneous melanoma - 98.2% (96.1% in 2021).

The share of stage IV cutaneous melanoma among all nosological forms of malignant neoplasms was 7.5%, occupying 17th rank in this indicator. The share of stage IV above the national average was noted in 10 regions of the country: Akmola - 30.0% (maximum level); Abay and Zhetysay - 21.4%; Mangystau - 20.0%;

Turkestan and Aktobe - 11.1%; Kostanay - 10.0%; Karaganda - 8.3%; Zhambyl and Shymkent city - 7.7%. The proportion of stage IV is less than the national average in 9 regions of the country, of which in 6 regions (Atyrau, East Kazakhstan, Kyzylorda, West Kazakhstan, North Kazakhstan, Pavlodar) advanced forms were not identified; Almaty – 5.9%; Astana city – 6.7% and Almaty city – 2.3%.

Now, as for the survival of patients. The number of patients under the supervision of oncological organizations in Kazakhstan for more than five years continued to grow and at the end of the reporting year amounted to 110,790 people, with an increase of 6.6% (2021 - 103,935 people, +4.4%) (form no. 7). The proportion of this category of patients or five-year survival rate for malignant neoplasms with a growth trend is 55.3% (55.0%).

As for cutaneous melanoma, at the end of 2022, 2,689 people, or 13.8 per 100 thousand population, were under observation at the dispensary. At the end of 2021 – 2590 patients and 13.5 per 100 thousand population, respectively. At the same time, the lethality of the observed contingents was 3.4 in 2022 and 4.1% in 2021. The five-year survival rate of patients with cutaneous melanoma was 60.5% in 2022 and 60.0% in 2021 [6].

Summarizing the above data, we can conclude that, being the “Queen of Tumors” and belonging to visually accessible localizations, cutaneous melanoma continues to remain a serious problem in modern clinical oncology, since, despite the efforts being made, the forecast for an increase in incidence rate and mortality from this type of malignant tumors is disappointing. All this requires both oncologists and, first of all, from medical staff of primary health care to increase the level of oncological alertness, inform the population about early symptoms that may indicate this pathology or the onset of proliferative changes and conduct other high-tech preventive and diagnostic events. An epidemiological assessment of the situation with cutaneous melanoma in our country suggests that there are sometimes

significant differences across regions not only in incidence rate, but also in the parameters of early diagnosis and mortality from this pathology. At the same time, it should be noted that cutaneous melanoma can be classified as one of the most actively detected tumors among all cancer localizations during preventive examinations with a significant increase compared to the level of the previous year.

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